

New Fundamental Principles for Physics

Paul Bernard White*

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Abstract

Starting from two plausible propositions about the construction of space, we show that dark energy must have some of the basic properties of a cosmological constant; namely, ubiquity and uniformity. Using those same propositions, we also derive the uniformity of space itself. From these results, we then abstract some general principles which, if incorporated into a model of the universe, promise much greater scope and explanatory power than what we are accustomed to. The reader is pointed to a longer exposition by the author which might be the prototype for such models.

Keywords: dark energy; cosmological constant; fundamental symmetries; independence relations; ontological priority

1 Introduction

The discovery of the expanding universe [1], and the more recent discovery of its acceleration [2, 3], mean that the creation of new space is a continuing aspect of our universe. The accelerated expansion is supposedly caused by a ubiquitous input of “dark energy” into the system. Currently, everyone is wondering what dark energy is, and where it comes from. Some simple reasoning below, however, might solve about 1/2 of this problem.

A cosmological constant, Λ , is the simplest candidate for dark energy [4]. It has four basic properties: (a) ubiquity, (b) uniformity, (c) it is constant in time, and (d) it is a scalar field. It turns out that we can *derive* the first two of these properties from a simple *a priori* argument, starting with the following propositions.

Proposition I: Space does not just magically come into existence. Rather, it is *constructed* by some process.

Proposition II: The process that constructs space is itself *independent of space*. (One could argue for this based on the need to avoid circularity.)

*Cottage Grove, Oregon (USA) ; pbwx@yahoo.com ; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2681-3670>

We assume that these two propositions hold no matter what the process for constructing space actually is, even if it is just “emergence” of some sort. Now let us proceed to use them for the purpose at hand.

2 Deriving two of the basic properties of Λ

Dark energy is an input of energy into the system that constructs new space. Suppose that the distribution of this energy is *nonuniform*, i.e. it is either anisotropic or inhomogeneous, or both. Such nonuniformity of distribution would imply that the process for constructing space is functionally *dependent* on space, thereby contradicting proposition II. We therefore conclude that the input of dark energy into the system must be perfectly *uniform* throughout space.

Moreover, due to this requirement for uniformity, we can also conclude that, if new space is being constructed by dark energy *anywhere*, then it must be constructed *everywhere* (i.e. ubiquity). Thus, dark energy must construct new space *uniformly everywhere* throughout space.

And so we conclude that dark energy must manifest as a ubiquitous, perfectly uniform, field – which gives us two of the four main properties of a cosmological constant.

As a corollary, we can then rule out *quantum-vacuum* energy as a contribution to dark energy (i.e., as a contribution to the process that constructs space), since it is *lumpy* on the small scale, and thus not perfectly uniform. Hence, by “cutting off” quantum-vacuum energy as a source of dark energy, propositions I and II might be part of a solution to the cosmological constant problem.

We have therefore obtained 1/2 of Λ 's basic properties with just simple *a priori* reasoning. We can consider this the “low-hanging fruit” of the problem, however. The other half of the problem, i.e. showing that the input of dark energy is also *constant in time* (and thus is a cosmological *constant*), and that it produces a *scalar* field, requires an actual model for how space and time are constructed, which can be found in [5] (e.g., in that paper we show that the input of dark energy is constant in time because the process that produces it is *independent of time*).

3 Deriving the uniformity of space

As a bonus, we can also derive the uniformity (isotropy and homogeneity) of space itself from the same reasoning above, as follows.

Suppose the process that constructs space (whatever it is) yields a space that is *nonuniform* (i.e. it is anisotropic or inhomogeneous, or both). Then the process that constructs space would be functionally *dependent* on space, thereby contradicting proposition II. We therefore conclude that, as constructed, space must be perfectly *uniform* (i.e. isotropic and homogeneous).

To my knowledge, this is the first *derivation* of spatial uniformity from first principles – which might indicate that we are uncovering here new, very fundamental, principles for how the universe is constructed.

4 Deriving symmetries (from underlying independence relations)

We note that proposition II is the statement of an *independence relation*. The reasoning above showed that this independence relation yields two basic symmetries: the uniformity of dark energy distribution, and the uniformity of ordinary space. These results suggest a new principle for physics: Rather than thinking of a symmetry itself as an ultimate fundamental, instead consider the possibility of an underlying (and more fundamental) independence relation as causing/producing the symmetry.

Indeed, a phenomenon that most physicists probably never thought of as a “symmetry”, namely the (default) smearing of particle locations across space (in quantum mechanics), is shown in [5] to be derivable from a close cousin to the independence relation that is stated in proposition II.

5 Ontological priority and subsequence

The reasoning above has elevated “independence relations” to fundamental significance – more fundamental than symmetries. But a more general concept, which inherently incorporates independence relations, is called *ontological priority*, which can be defined as follows [6].

“*A is ontologically prior to B*” means that: *A* is (existentially) *independent* of *B*, whereas *B* is (existentially) *dependent* on *A*. (Alternatively, we may convey the same meaning by saying that “*B* is ontologically *subsequent* to *A*”.)

So, a more general version of proposition II would be:

Proposition III: The process that constructs space is **ontologically prior** to space. (From which proposition II is easily obtained via the definition of ontological priority given above.)

Thus, ontological priority generates independence relations, which generate symmetries; and so the former (ontological priority) can be considered as the most fundamental of these.

Moreover, relations of ontological priority and subsequence offer a new type of *ordering* principle for constructing the physical universe, by which we can avoid the trap of reflexively describing everything in *spatio-temporal* terms. The big bang theory, for example, is a model of the universe in terms of spatio-temporal relations and ordering, and thus has a limited compass; e.g., it cannot talk meaningfully about $t = 0$, nor “prior” to it. A *fundamental* model of the universe must include such primordia within its purview, and so must incorporate a more fundamental type of ordering relation, which ontological priority and subsequence seem to provide.

In summary, if you want a model of the universe that is capable of *deriving* basic symmetries (instead of just assuming them), and in general is capable of explaining phenomena that otherwise seem unexplainable, then a promising strategy is to incorporate relations of ontological priority and subsequence into the very fabric of the model.

6 Conclusion

Acceptance of propositions I and II means that dark energy (whatever its source might be) necessarily has two of the four basic properties of a cosmological constant: ubiquity and uniformity. In addition, we also get the uniformity of space as a bonus, and eliminate at least some of the cosmological constant problem.

Moreover, a model for constructing the physical universe in which the primitive elements (whatever they might be) are related by ontological priority and subsequence has the prospect of much greater scope and explanatory power than what we are accustomed to. The model presented in [5] might be prototypical in that regard.

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